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Research Article

**PHYTOCHEMICAL SCREENING AND IN VITRO
ANTHELMINTIC ACTIVITY OF SOLANUM LYSCOPERSICUM
FRUIT EXTRACT****Arjumand Ara^{1*}, Afzalunnisa Begum², Mohd Zubair³, Madiha Shahveen⁴, Mohd Abdul
Azeem⁵, Shafiya Sultana⁶, Sahera Sultana⁷**

Deccan School of Pharmacy, Darussalam, Aghapura, Nampally, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Article Received: June 2024**Accepted: June 2024****Published: July 2024****Abstract:**

Traditional Indian medicine is gaining popularity worldwide. Medicinal plants can enhance patients' symptoms by reducing the side effects of synthetic drugs, thereby enhancing their quality of life. *Solanum lycopersicum* (Tomato) is a perennial flowering plant in the Family Solanaceae. Tomato is one of the most important and popular fruit vegetable in the world. The aim of present research work is to assess the phytochemical investigation and in vitro anthelmintic activity of ethanolic extract of *Solanum lycopersicum* fruit. In vitro anthelmintic activity of *Solanum lycopersicum* (*S. lycopersicum*) were screened using different concentrations separately. *Pheretima posthuma* (Indian earth worm) of nearly equal size were selected for present study. Albendazole is used as standard drug. The *S. lycopersicum* extract was concentrated on in various fixations (100, 200 and 400 mg/ml) anthelmintic movement on *Pheretima posthuma* worms. The ethanoic fruit extract of *Solanum lycopersicum* showed significant anthelmintic activity against earth worms. Further work will emphasize the isolation and characterization of active principles responsible for anthelmintic activity of *Solanum lycopersicum*.

Key words: *Solanum lycopersicum*, traditional medicine, phytoconstituents, anthelmintic activity, *Pheretima posthuma*.

Corresponding author:**Arjumand Ara,**

Assistant Professor

Department of Pharmacognosy,

Deccan School of Pharmacy,

Darussalam, Aghapura, Nampally, Hyderabad, Telangana, India-500 001.

E-Mail: ara.pharmacy@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Restorative plants play a vital role in global healthcare due to their believed therapeutic and healing properties. These medicinal plants are widely used for treating diseases and endorsing a healthier lifestyle. More than two-thirds of the global population depend on plant-based treatments for primary healthcare because of their cultural significance and patient compliance. These alternative medicines characteristically comprise of plant extracts and natural constituents, with herbal drugs derived from plants holding significant therapeutic value. The use of plants as a source of medicine is a primeval practice and an important aspect of healthcare systems in India. Many drugs are either plant-based or contain active pharmaceutical ingredients derived from plant extracts [1,2].

In traditional medical treatments, a vast range of medicinal plants are used, with approximately 70% of the population relying on them. India, one of the 17 mega-diverse countries, has an abundant supply of medicinal plants used for traditional treatments. Over 20,000 medicinal plants have been documented, but practitioners regularly use only 7,000-7,500 of them. Around 26,000 plant-based formulations are effectually utilized in traditional medicine, with about 1.5 million practitioners employing this traditional medical system for healthcare in India [3,4].

A disease such as “Helminthiasis” where modern drug therapy has not accomplished complete cure is an important aim of ethnopharmacological research. Better and safer medicines can be developed by isolation and testing of by active compounds from medicinal plants. Helminthiasis occurs in the small

intestine. It is the most common disorder. This condition is difficult to control with any single drug therapy and complete cure cannot be achieved. Even after discontinuation of drug, the relapse rate is high, and long-term use of synthetic drugs produces adverse effects on the human body. Based on the ethnomedical uses, *Solanum lycopersicum* (*S. lycopersicum*, Tomato) was selected for its presences of carotenoids, tocopherols, lysine, arginine, pectin, linoleic acid, alpha and beta tomatine, which are known to have anti-inflammatory, anti-oxidant and wound healing properties [5,6].

Tomato (*Solanum lycopersicum* L.) is one of the most imperative and common fruit vegetable in the world. *Solanum lycopersicum* (Tomato) is the flowering plant of the nightshade family (Solanaceae), cultivated broadly for its edible fruits. Tomato plants are perennials in their native habitat, it is used in the treatment of cancer. Tomatoes are widely used in culinary traditions around the world. In traditional medicine systems like Ayurveda and Traditional Chinese Medicine (TCM), tomatoes have been used for their medicinal properties. They are believed to alleviate conditions like inflammation, digestive issues, urinary tract problems, rheumatism, influenza, hay fever, diarrhea, and have cooling properties. The high content of vitamin C, lycopene, and other anti-oxidants in tomatoes is believed to protect the eyes from oxidative damage and support vision health. Some cultures have used tomatoes in skin care routines. For example, in parts of Asia, tomato pulp or juice is applied to the skin to relieve sun burn, soothe skin irritations, and promote overall skin health due to its anti-oxidant and acidic properties [7-10].

Figure 1: *Solanum lycopersicum* plant

Figure 2: *Solanum lycopersicum* fruit

The aim of present study is to assess the phytochemical investigation and *in vitro* anthelmintic activity of ethanolic extract of *Solanum lycopersicum* fruit.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection of plant material:

The sun-dried *Solanum lycopersicum* (Tomato) was ordered online on Amazon which was repacked and marketed by Natulix India Marketing B-01, Trinetra Apartment, BP Cross Road, Kharigaon Bhayandar East, Thane, Maharashtra, India.

Method of extraction:

Around 200 g of dried *Solanum lycopersicum* was weighed, powdered using a mixer grinder, and passed through Sieve No. 80. The coarse powder was separated with ethanol in Soxhlet's apparatus at a temperature not exceeding 70 °C for 10 h. The concentrate was concentrated utilizing simple distillation to yield a crude, semi-solid mass. In the wake of drying the concentrates was utilized for phytochemical and *in vitro* pharmacological screening [11,12].

Figure 3: Soxhlet apparatus for extraction

Preliminary phytochemical screening:

The extract obtained was subjected to qualitative chemical test for the identification of various chemical constituents by using standard procedure [13-15].

In vitro anthelmintic activity screening [16-18]:

In vitro anthelmintic activity of *Solanum lycopersicum* (*S. lycopersicum*) were screened using different concentrations separately. *Pheretima posthuma* (Indian earth worm) of nearly equal size were selected for present study due to its anatomical and physiological resemblance with the intestinal roundworm parasites of human beings. Albendazole as the standard medication 20 mg/ml. Ethanolic concentrates of *Solanum lycopersicum* were additionally weakened to get 100, 200 and 400 mg/ml fixations are chosen for studies. Typical saline alone filled in as dissolvable control. Control group was treated with 0.1 g gum acacia in buffered saline.

Albendazole suspension was utilized as a standard medication at a fixation 20 mg/ml.

The *Solanum lycopersicum* separate were ready in expanding focus (100, 200, and 400 mg/ml) and it is taken as test group. All these dilutions were poured into the petri dishes accordingly. 5 Gatherings of worms (n-5) were taken for the review. Perceptions were made for the time taken to deaden and paralyzing the worm as long as four hours of trial. Loss of motion was said to happen when the worms didn't restore even in ordinary saline. Passing was closed when the worms lost their motility followed with disappearing of their body tone.

Group 1: Normal control group using normal saline 0.5% w/v + 0.1 g gum acacia

Group 2: Standard group albendazole 20 mg/ml

Group 3: Saline + ethanolic extract 100 mg/ml

Group 4: Saline + ethanolic extract 200 mg/ml

Group 5: Saline + ethanolic extract 400 mg/ml

RESULTS:**Yield of extraction:**

Percentage yield of extractives was calculated using the formula;

$$\begin{aligned} \% \text{ Yield} &= \frac{\text{Weight of extract}}{\text{Weight of crude drug}} \times 100 \\ &= \frac{47.91}{200} \times 100 \\ &= 23.95\% \end{aligned}$$

Preliminary phytochemical analysis:

The subjective compound examination for *S. lycopersicum* remove was done to identify the presence of different phytoconstituents. *S. lycopersicum* showed the presence of alkaloids, starch, steroids, proteins and amino corrosive, flavonoids, phenols, glycosides, carotenoids, and unsaturated fats and oils.

Table 1: Phytochemical constituents of *S. lycopersicum*

S. No.	Chemical constituents	Ethanol extract
1	Alkaloids	+
2	Glycosides	+
3	Phenols	+
4	Flavonoids	+
5	Steroids	+
6	Fatty acids and oils	+
7	Proteins and amino acids	+
8	Carbohydrates	+
9	Carotenoids	+

'+' indicates present, '-' indicates absent

Anthelmintic activity:

The *S. lycopersicum* extract was concentrated on in various fixations (100, 200 and 400 mg/ml) anthelmintic movement on *Pheretima posthuma* worms. Separate shows a critical action in a portion subordinate way as displayed in Figure 5. The anthelmintic movement of *S. lycopersicum* separate in lower fixation isn't critical, in higher concentration extract of 200 and 400 mg/ml showed 20.34±3.87 and 14.9±3.23 minutes loss of motion time separately

when contrasted with the standard albendazole which was 15.10±2.38 min.

The passing time recorded was 47.1±4.69 and 42.9±3.47 min separately in contrast with the standard which was recorded to be 41.39±4.12 min. Adequacy of the concentrate *S. lycopersicum* was conversely corresponding to the ideal opportunity for loss of motion (vermifuge) and demise (vermicidal) of the worms.

Figure 4: Anthelmintic activity of *S. lycopersicum* fruit

Figure 5: Anthelmintic activity of *S. lycopersicum* fruit with standard drug albendazole

DISCUSSION:

Scientists have long preferred natural sources like plants and herbs for discovering and developing medicines because they contain various beneficial compounds. Plant-based medicines are generally considered safe and are used to treat many ailments. Numerous studies have shown that many plants have compounds effective against various pathogens. *Solanum lycopersicum* consists of many bioactive compounds such as phenolics (flavonoids-rutin, naringenin, kaempferol, quercetin, and phenolic acids-chlorogenic acid), carotenoids (lutein, alpha-carotene, β -carotene and lycopene), vitamin A, B, and E, minerals (K, Na, Mg, and S), proteins (glutamic acid and aspartic acid), amino acids (lysine, histidine, alanine, valine, leucine, isoleucine and phenylalanine), fatty acids (linoleic acid, oleic acids and palmitic acids), and glycoalkaloids (tomatine and solanine).

Roundworm, a common type of helminth, infects around 35% of the global population according to the World Health Organization. These infections spread through contaminated soil, food, water, feces, and contact with contaminated objects. Scientists are actively looking for new treatments, including from plant sources. Our anthelmintic studies showed that fruit extract of *S. lycopersicum* in concentration range of 200 mg/ml and 400 mg/ml showed significant result compare to standard anthelmintic drug albendazole.

CONCLUSION:

S. lycopersicum is among the most commonly used herb in the history of mankind. The results of the present study point to then need for a careful evaluation of the phytotherapeutic product in researching even when it may be widely used by the Population. The ethanolic extract of the tomato leaves was more effective even at lower concentrations in causing paralysis and death of earthworms than the standard drug, albendazole. It can be concluded that active constituents responsible for anthelmintic activity are present in the ethanolic extract of leaves of *Solanum lycopersicum*. Albendazole is likely to work by inhibiting microtubule synthesis. It binds to the parasite's β -tubulin and prevents its polymerization. This suggests that the anthelmintic effectiveness of certain drugs could be influenced by the presence of specific genes, phytochemicals, and mutations. Tropical medicines are predominantly used to treat these severe diseases.

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